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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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When the Community Became My Classroom

In the heart of every nursing student's quest,
Community immersion puts them to the test.
From classroom walls to the world outside,
They step with excitement, and a hint of pride.
Yet nerves may whisper as they learn each day,
To navigate new paths in a different way.

Amid real lives and stories shared,
They see how deeply healthcare is paired
With homes, with struggles, with daily strife
The social threads that shape a life.
They gather data, assess with care,
And find public health woven everywhere.
With every challenge, they learn to adjust,
To think with compassion, to lead with trust.

In distant GIDA communities they stand,
Where need is great and hope is fanned.
They witness battles silently fought,
In access denied, in care long sought.
Through every moment, their hearts expand,
Empathy growing hand in hand.
They learn the cultures, the beliefs held dear,
And offer care that is warm and clear.

A calling awakened, a place they belong.
For nursing is more than healing pain
It's lifting others again and again.
It's knowing each life they're privileged to touch
Can mean everything and that means so much...